
INFORMATION AND CONTENT ASPECT OF SPEECH VERBS

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Annotation

This article is about a contrastive analysis of the lexical field of verbs of speaking in English and Uzbek. The main goal is to explore what similarities and differences are present within the lexical field in the two languages.

Key words

verbs of speaking, lexical field, contrastive analysis, componential analysis, semantic features.

Verbs are used to express a state or an action. For example, they show what people or things do, think or feel. Verbs are one of the eight parts of speech, or nine parts of speech. Verbs are used to express an action.

This article is a contrastive analysis of the lexical field of verbs of speaking in English and Uzbek. The main goal is to explore what similarities and differences are present within the lexical field in the two languages. Lexemes are first contrasted within one language, in order to explore the features that distinguish verbs of speaking one from the other. The meaning of verbs is analyzed by the procedure of componential analysis, by decomposing meaning into its component parts.

Accordingly, English verbs are classified into semantically similar groups and analyzed one by one, with suggested corresponding Uzbek equivalents. The paper tries to offer a more precise transfer of meaning of the verbs of speaking from one language to another and to provide solutions to the process of translation. The results obtained show that all the English verbs in the research have their formal correspondent in Uzbek, while some of the verbs also have their translation equivalents.

The analysis, therefore, may contribute to a more precise transfer of meaning of these verbs from one language to another during the process of translation.

Evaluative, quantitative, modal, attributive and other features appear in the object category. For example:

—You may place considerable confidence in Mr. Holmes, sir, said the police agent loftily. —He has his own little methods, which are, if he won't mind my saying so, just a little too theoretical and fantastic, but he has the makings of a detective in him. It is not too much to say that once or twice, as in that business of the Sholto murder and the Agra treasure, he has been more nearly correct than the official force.(Arthur Conan Doyle, The red-headed league).

"I am not religious," he said. "But I will say ten Our Fathers and ten Hail Marys that I should catch this fish, and I promise to make a pilgrimage to the Virgin of Cobre if I catch him. That is a promise." He commenced to say his prayers mechanically. Sometimes he would be so tired that he could not remember the prayer and then he would say them fast so that they would come automatically. Hail Mary's are easier to say than Our Fathers, he thought. (ERNEST HEMINGWAY, The old man and the sea).

- Men hamma yaxshi tilaklarga qo'shilaman, shu bilan birga o'zim ham kichkina bir tilakni aytmoqchiman. Men oila qurganim yo'q, lekin ko'p oilalarga razm solib bir fikrga keldim. Bilmadim, vaqti kelganda bu fikrimni o'zim amalga oshira olamanmi, yo'qmi... Lekin, shundoq boisa ham, do'stim Salimjon bilan kelinimiz Muhayyoxonga shuni aytmoqchiman: qadimdan oilada er general, xotin soldat bo`lib kelgan ekan, endilikda xotinlardan ham generallar chiqayotibdi-ku, lekin erkaklar soldat bo`lgani uncha unashmayapti... (Abdulla Qahhor, Anor).

Nutq fe'llari ham o`zbek, ham ingliz tillarida baholovchi (masalan, safsata, bo`lmagan gap, va sh.k. /

Verbs of speech are evaluative in both English and Uzbek languages (for example: nonsense, rubbish, rot, quibbling/safsata, bo`lmagan gap) comes together with nouns. In them, the information is combined with the assessment.

For example:

Muhayyo ham qizarib yerga qaradi va eshitar-eshitilmas dedi: — Nega xafa bo`lar ekanman, shunday vaqtda, shunday paytda shunaqa bo`lmagan gaplarni o'zingiz aytmoqchi, haqoratlarga o'zlarini tutib beradilaru...- uning o'pkasi to`ldi, - ola o`lgunimcha esimdan chiqadimi... Rahimjon yolg'ondan qovogini solib so'radi: — Shunda farishtalar omin degan boisa-chi? (Abdulla Qahhor, Anor).

Alice had learnt several things of this sort in her lessons in the schoolroom, and though this was not a very good opportunity for showing off her knowledge, as there was no one to listen to her, still it was good practice to say it over) — yes, that's about the right distance — but then I wonder what Latitude or Longitude I've

got to?' (Alice had no idea what Latitude was, or Longitude either, but thought they were nonsense words to say. Lewis Carroll. Alice's Adventures in Wonderland.

For example:

Verbs of speech with nouns determine information about the actions and relationships of interlocutors: biror yoqimli, dalda beruvchi, meprli, do`stona, chin yurakdan/to say something pleasant, encouraging, kind, friendly, from the heart, etc.

Endi chekinmasa bo`lmaydi. Itning fe'li egasiga ma'lum, deganlariday, Nasiba erining odatini biladi. Qachonki, ishxonada yo ko`chada noxushlikka duch kelsa, alamini uydand oladi, keyin hasratini to`kadi. Meni ham odam qatoriga qo`shishibdi.

– Sharif biror yoqimli narsa gapirmoqchi edi, uddalay olmadi. So`zlari labidan titrabroq uchdi. (Tohir Malik, Shaytanat).

– Qo`lingizni oling! – dedim yana zarda bilan.

– To`rtta bolam bor. Oladigan narsalaringizni oling-da, keting!

– Qanaqa narsalarni? – deb hayron bo`lib menga qaradi u.

– Manavi taqinchoqlarni. Zirak, uzuk. Sumkada ham bor. Mana. Sumkani ochib ko`rsatdim. Sumkaning ichi yaltirab ketdi.

– Meni kim deb o`ylayapsiz, xonim!

– U qoshlarini chimirdi. – Agar yuz gramm ortiqcha ichgan bo`lsam, ikki... atigi ikki og`iz shirin gap gapirmoqchi bo`lgan bo`lsam, darrov meni tuppa-tuzuk odamni o`g`riga chiqarib qo`yasizmi? (O'lmas Umarbekov, Saylanma).

We began cheerfully, one might almost say about it skittishly, but our light-heartedness was gone by the time the first potato was finished. (Jerome K. Jerome, Three Men in a Boat).

I might well say now, indeed, that the latter end of Job was better than the beginning. It is impossible to express the fluttering of my very heart when I found all my wealth about me; for as the Brazil ships come all in fleets, the same ships which brought my letters brought my goods: and the effects were safe in the river before the letters came to my hand. In a word, I turned pale, and grew sick; and, had not the old man run and fetched me a cordial, I believe the sudden surprise of joy had overset nature, and I had died upon the spot: nay, after that I continued very ill, and was so some hours, till a physician being sent for, and something of the real cause of my illness being known, he ordered me to be let blood; after which I had relief, and grew well: but I verify believe, if I had not been eased by a vent

given in that manner to the spirits, I should have died. (Daniel Defoe, Robinson Crusoe)

In this case, intentionality includes encouraging, helping, cheering or knocking on the ground, insulting someone, and similar speech acts given in a veiled form. There are some differences between the English and Uzbek languages that are being compared. Among them, you can include such nouns as bitter, slanderous words, disrespectful words, words that sink, cut off words, and kind words.

In English, they are not used with speech verbs, but with verbs belonging to other semantic classes: to pay a compliment, to be impudent, to make witty remarks, to make caustic remarks:

For example:

'Well; what about the boy?'. 'Oh!' replied the undertaker; 'why, you know, Mr. Bumble, I pay a compliment. (Charles Dickens, Oliver Twist or the parish boy's progress)

Idioethnic features are also observed when giving voluminous information: speaking/saying a word, a toast /so`z, tost gapirmoq/aytmoq / to deliver a speech, to make a speech, to give a report, to propose a toast to smth., (smb.).

For example:

– Xo`ja Xalifa shuni masjidi jomeda minbarga chiqib so`z aytmoqchi bo`lgan ekan, «Yolg`on! Kofirlar xati harom! Qur`on ursin sen Xalifani!» deyishib, johillar uni minbardan tortib tushirmishlar. Agar Tohibek boshliq soqchilarimiz Xo`ja Xalifani qutqarib qolmasalar, johillar uni ham o`ldirishlari mumkin ekan. (Pirimqul Qodirov, Yulduzli tunlar).

In speech activity, the modality aspect of information (for example, speaking/telling the truth, truth, lie) to tell the truth, to tell a lie) and the number aspect (for example, one mouth, two mouths it is extremely important to show.

For example:

'Say a word to her,' Dr Macphail whispered to his wife. 'She's all alone here, and it seems rather unkind to ignore her.' Mrs. Macphail was shy, but she was in the habit of doing what her husband bade her. (W. Somerset Maugham, Rain).

The neighborhood of Streatley and Goring is a great fishing centre. There is some excellent fishing to be had here. The river abounds in pike, roach, dace, gudgeon, and eels, just here; and you can sit and fish for them all day. Some people do. They never catch them. I never knew anybody catch anything, up the Thames, except minnows and dead cats, but that has nothing to do, of course, with fishing! The local fisherman's guide doesn't say a word about catching anything. (Jerome K. Jerome, Three Men in a Boat).

‘Father Brown,’ said the secretary, who had recovered his quiet tone, ‘you’re very smart, but there’s something more to you than smartness. Somehow you’re the sort of man to whom one wants to tell the truth; and besides, you’ll probably hear it, anyhow, for in one way it’s a joke against me already. They all say I’m a monomaniac about running down this big crook, and perhaps I am. (G. K. Chesterton, *The Arrow of Heaven*).

All the local fisherman's guide says is the place is "a good station for fishing;" and, from what I have seen of the district, I am quite prepared to bear out this statement. (Jerome K. Jerome, *Three Men in a Boat*).

The functional-cognitive potential of verbs in English and Uzbek languages is almost the same. Speech verbs aimed at the functions of speech activity and language tasks determine their complex meaning system. This broad meaning structure concretizes aspects of the global concept of "to speak". The wide functional-cognitive potential of speech verbs is based on the fact that the functions of speech activity and language tasks are in communication with each other and are closely connected. Informational, subjective, and intentional aspects of speech appear as language universals.

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